

Original Article

Post-Conflict Recovery and Rehabilitation: An Alternative Psycho-Social Approach

Rabia Fayyaz¹ & Jamil Ahmad Chitrali²

¹ PhD Scholar, Institute of Peace & Conflict Studies, University of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

² Professor of Sociology, Institute of Peace & Conflict Studies, University of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Abstract

The prolonged exposure to violence in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa challenges the mental health of its population more than any other provinces in the country (Khan et al, 2018) found that 75% children suffered from PTSD after Army Public School Massacre, while 23% people of KP suffered from PTSD due to terrorism in 2013. The estimated population that suffered from war on terror from 2005 till 2022, including death toll and injuries, are reported as 46,028 civilians and security forces personnel from KP and newly merged tribal districts, while total number of terrorism related incidents are reported as 13,035 (South Asia Terrorism Portal, 2023). On the other hand, Pakistan has less than 500 psychiatrists for 249 million people, leaving behind more than 90% population untreated (Sehat Kahani, 2022). There is a lack of trained psychiatrist as consultants in the country, hence, no training could be conducted in specialized fields like forensic psychiatry, geriatric psychiatry, child psychiatry, learning disability, psychotherapy, and drug and alcohol abuse. Counseling, along with an eclectic approach, is mostly used by psychologists due to a lack of training in psychotherapies. Trained clinical psychologists could be utilized in the improvement of counseling and psychotherapy. Due to the dearth of specialists, the family in Pakistan is an important resource for looking after the patients. To improve patient care, families could be utilized and considered an important resource (WHO-AIMS Report, 2009), which is the point of debate as alternative psycho-social approach for post-conflict recovery and rehabilitation.

Keywords: Post-Conflict Recovery, Alternative Mental Healthcare, Rehabilitation, Family Therapy and Peer Support

Introduction

Pakistan has brought many reforms to the healthcare system; however, it is still struggling with numerous challenges like lack of access to healthcare services, unequal resources, poor governance, corruption, inadequate health information management system, shortage of trained staff, and lack of monitoring in health policy and planning (Kurji, Premani, & Mithani, 2016). The same is the case with mental healthcare, as it is also functioning ineffectively and results in compromised health outcomes (WHO, 2009). More than 90% of individuals with common mental disorders remain untreated due to a dearth of mental health professionals and stigma about mental health (Sikander, 2020).

According to the Data Collection Survey on Health Facilities & Equipment in the Islamic Republic of Pakistan Report (2018), health services are provided in four broad categories at basic health facilities or public hospitals including, (i) Primary healthcare mechanism which comprises mother and child health centers and sub-health centers, dispensaries, basic health units (BHU), rural health centers (RHC); (ii) Secondary healthcare mechanism which comprises tehsil headquarters hospital (THQ), the district headquarters hospital (DHQ); (iii) Tertiary healthcare mechanism which comprises tertiary hospitals; and (iv) Private clinical set-ups. There are 1,349 primary healthcare centers, 125 secondary healthcare hospitals, and 08 tertiary healthcare hospitals in KP for a population

JOURNAL OF
SOCIAL HORIZONS

Copyright © The Author(s). 2025

This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author(s) and source are credited.

How to Cite:

Fayyaz, R., & Chitrali, J. A. (2025). Post-Conflict Recovery and Rehabilitation: An Alternative Psycho-Social Approach. *Journal of Social Horizons*, 2(2), 1-10.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15358681>

* Corresponding Author: Jamil Ahmad Chitrali | Professor of Sociology, Institute of Peace & Conflict Studies, University of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

✉ jamilchitrali@uop.edu.pk

© 2025 | College of Education, Swabi, Pakistan.

of 40.8 million according to the 2023 census. Psychiatry Units and Psychiatrists could only be found in the Tertiary care (8 in total) or the DHQ hospitals (around 125 in total) in KP, and that too in a very small number (DHIS Annual Report, 2017).

Due to a shortage of mental health practitioners in the primary health centers, medical doctors, nurses, and healthcare workers are given training in mental health. 27% of the training for medical doctors is devoted to mental health, in comparison to 3% of nurses and 11% of non-doctor/non-nurse primary health care workers. The assessment and treatment protocols of major mental disorders are available in a few (21-50%) doctor-based primary healthcare centers. Only 21-50% of primary healthcare doctors refer (on average) one patient per month to a mental health expert, while centers that lack medical doctors do not refer mental health patients to experts. 1-20% of doctor-based primary health centers interact with alternative or traditional practitioners instead of mental health facilities. There are no restrictions on doctors in primary health centers to prescribe psychotropic medications (WHO-AIMS Report, 2009).

Theoretical Framework

Social Support Theory, primarily developed by Sheldon Cohen in the 1980s and 1990s, builds upon earlier contributions by Sidney Cobb and John Cassel in the 1970s. The theory emphasizes that social support serves as a crucial buffer against stress and plays a significant role in promoting both mental and physical well-being. It categorizes support into three main types: instrumental support, which includes practical or material assistance; informational support, which offers advice or guidance; and emotional support, which provides empathy, trust, and reassurance. The buffering hypothesis within the theory suggests that social support protects individuals from the harmful effects of stress, while the main effects hypothesis argues that being part of a social network positively influences health outcomes regardless of stress levels, by instilling a sense of belonging and encouraging healthy behaviors through social norms and peer influence.

Furthermore, the theory makes a distinction between perceived support—the belief that support is available when needed—and received support—the actual aid provided—emphasizing that perceived support is often more effective in relieving stress and promoting health. However, the theory also acknowledges that social networks are not always beneficial. Negative interactions within these networks—such as conflict, exploitation, stress transmission, or misguided help—can become psychological stressors themselves. These harmful dynamics may impair emotional, cognitive, and physiological health, highlighting that the quality of social support is just as important as its presence

Research Question

This study derives its crux through the question, how does the family institution function as an alternative coping mechanism or treatment intervention for individual growth and psychological recovery in times of stress? The family institution can be viewed as a primary source of emotional, instrumental, and informational support. Families provide care, empathy, guidance, and practical help, all of which play a vital role in helping individuals cope with stress and recover from difficult life events or mental health challenges. As an alternative coping mechanism or treatment intervention, family support can foster a sense of belonging, emotional security, and motivation for healthy behaviors. The consistent presence of family members may enhance perceived support, which research shows is more effective than received support in reducing stress and improving health outcomes. Therefore, exploring how family systems function as a supportive network can offer valuable insights for designing effective interventions aimed at individual growth and recovery.

Research Objective

- To describe the family institution as an alternative coping mechanism/treatment intervention for growth and recovery.

Methodology

The study is BASED on in-depth interviews, as case studies, with persons experiencing Posttraumatic Growth. The sample is divided into three broad categories i.e. (i) traumatized civilians; (ii) traumatized non-civilians; and (iii) bereaved families, with equal representation to draw necessary conclusions. The civilian population comprises all adult (above 18) individuals, both male and female, who are not in any government service, including both civil

and military. Whereas the non-civilian population includes police officers, military personnel, and government employees (e.g., doctors, teachers, bureaucrats) who are considered responsible for public safety and order. Lastly, the bereaved families refer to “those families who have lost their loved ones due to a traumatic event”.

Findings

In the regions like Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP), where formal mental healthcare systems are limited, alternative coping mechanisms, such as family and social support networks, play a critical role in the recovery of individuals affected by political violence. In the absence of trained professionals, informal support systems such as family members, peers, community elders, and religious leaders take on the responsibility of identifying mental health issues, offering counseling, motivation, and providing referrals (Farwell & Cole, 2001). These support networks, deeply embedded in cultural practices, often provide the first line of care and play a significant role in emotional and psychological healing. They offer an alternative model to formal healthcare, drawing on community-driven interventions and cultural traditions to meet the psychological needs of survivors (Sohail et al., 2017). As a significant portion of KP’s population resides in rural areas with limited access to psychiatric services, people often turn to informal networks for support. Literature indicates that such support systems—although not formally trained—can offer therapeutic benefits like clinical interventions (Sashidharan et al., 2016). Community-based approaches, such as task-sharing, have been recognized globally as effective strategies in lower- and middle-income countries (Sashidharan et al., 2016). In KP, where traditional beliefs about mental illness, such as the influence of the evil eye or supernatural forces, shape how distress is understood, informal support mechanisms often replace formal psychiatric care (Sohail et al., 2017). This cultural context influences how survivors seek help and find relief in their communities, making family and religious leaders are essential players in the healing process.

Discussion

The alternative mental health treatments provided by these informal networks have been identified through survivor narratives, which emphasize five key themes: (i) family support as primary mental healthcare, (ii) religious and cultural coping mechanisms, (iii) community-driven healing processes, (iv) rebuilding through education and future planning, and (v) miscellaneous alternative mechanisms. These themes highlight the multifaceted role of community in supporting recovery (De Zulueta, 2007). Informal interventions, while not formalized, often complement the formal mental health care system and provide vital psychological support where it is most needed. The study suggests that integrating these informal networks with professional care could strengthen mental health outcomes for individuals impacted by political violence in regions like KP (Sashidharan et al., 2016).

Family Support as Primary Mental Health Care / Family as First Responders

War and political violence result in disturbing sensory images, lack of a secure base, chaos, disrupted social structures, broken rules, loss and immense sadness, and loss of meaning. All these symptoms pose a psychological threat to an individual’s development. Mental health programs are usually not effective in promoting coping and better functioning in life-related tasks for the war-affected people. The family and community ensure good functioning and handling of life tasks for the individuals and children. It also supports the recovery and reintegration of the affected individuals. Community influences the appraisals, feelings, and coping responses of the individuals. Community plays the role of uniting its members for their healing and productive outcomes during the times of post-conflict reconstruction (Farwell & Cole, 2001).

Emotional Availability and Comfort

A 40-year-old survivor of target killing from South Waziristan district of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province in Pakistan, a terrorism prone region, where mental healthcare is extremely scarce, and people do not access professional psychological services due to a lack of awareness and concerns about holding traditional masculine standards. The survivor briefed his recovery journey by saying:

“My aunt used to look after me like a mother. She motivated me by reassuring me that I would be fine, as I was being shot twice near my chest by two men wearing masks in a market in Waziristan. She was always around me, looking after my needs. She would soup for me to keep me warm because it was winter. Her care not only

provided me with physical relief but also provided me with mental peace” (Field Interview with a survivor of multiple target-killing attacks in South Waziristan).

Falloon (2003) suggests in their study that effective communication skills used by the relatives towards the patients, for instance, expressing positive comments when patients make trivial efforts, encourage them to improve, and avoiding hostile criticism and irritable remarks to the patients, motivates them to solve their problems. The study provided insight into the significance of effective nursing and rehabilitation approaches adapted by the family members. Hence, family interventions are effective in adult mental health, specifically when the capacity of family members is increased through psychoeducation or training in stress management. In Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province the survivor gets support from kin nurses who are not trained in the formal institutes but through family chores, cultural practices and value system. They do not have any psychological training, but their presence, consistent nursing, constantly listening, and the understanding for patients’ need fulfillment helps more than anything. In the field quote above, one can observe that she never criticized him while comforted him with effective communication. This resembles formal mental healthcare services where a trained psychologist is engaged in active listening, reflective responses, and grounding techniques with a patient. His aunt’s emotional presence provided empathy, safety, and validation, like providing psychotherapeutic techniques in an informal setting.

A bereaved 50 year old father described that after his son’s death (martyrdom) in 2016, his grandfather could not bear the pain of loss [of the grandson] and fell sick and died too. This put a lot of pressure on his shoulders as he needed his father’s backing and support the most in that time of crisis and felt weak to not have a man’s [father’s] support by his side. Those years were too tough on his mental health due to the distress. He reported that two years later, in 2018, the birth of a second son incredibly changed his life. He recounted, “Thanks to Allah [God], amidst all this [crises], a happy moment also arrived, which was the birth of my son in 2018. My wife was also very happy at the birth of my second son. His birth provided a ray of hope to me and my wife’ happiness” (field notes). This suggests that a son’s birth serves as “hope replacement”, a healing component for the bereaved parents in a patriarchal society where a son’s birth is celebrated more than that of a girl child, and a son is considered a source of support for the parents in their old age. He believed that family support is significant than any other support mechanism in tough times of life, “A friend is after all a friend, he does not live in your home [implying that out of home people cannot understand your problems as best as family members]”. This suggests that family holds a significant healing power for the recovery of traumatized individuals because they can offer practical and daily life support, motivation, and emotional healing better than any other services.

Restoring Routine and Sense of Normalcy

Resuming back to a previous routine post-conflict is difficult, but the family’s motivation can assist. A father-in-law motivated his daughter-in-law [bereaved mother of a martyred son] to not rely on psychotropic medications for her wellness, but rather rely on her strengths. She reported “I have attended few counseling sessions, I had taken [psychotropic] medications in the start, then my father-in-law asked me not to rely on medicines as it is like pushing myself into a deep well, rather he asked me to come out of it [distress] by pushing myself out, because I have children, home, and everything to look after to”, these words motivated her a lot and she got the courage to rely on her strength after receiving a push from her father-in-law (“N”, 43 years, Bereaved Mother of Martyred Son). Trauma of one family member in the conflict results in traumatizing the whole family, and these traumatic experiences result in feelings of helplessness, night horror, hatred, and irritation. The family has therapeutic potential in overcoming such traumatic consequences by sharing resources, overcoming obstacles, restoring psychological harmony, and cooperation. Family offers love, respect, acceptance, support, mutual understanding, emotional warmth, and psychological defense to other family members. All of these are necessary therapeutic components that enhance the emotional stability of the family and help in the psychological well-being. In contrast, if a family fails to provide these components, it may result in behavioral and emotional problems within family members (Kliapets, 2015).

Accepting the fact that “life is perishable” helped a young survivor of a terrorist attack relive his life once again. He had lost his elder brother in the same incident and was in grief and despair. He said that he had no other choice but to recover; he regained his hope in life by realizing that:

“I thought we only get one life... and I had already spent 19 years of my life. I also wanted to spend my life well, so that when I reach the end of my life, I am satisfied with how I spent it fearlessly and not in distress. I knew that I had to die [one day], which would happen anyway, whether I am happy or sad, so I wanted to achieve

something in life, which was only possible by overcoming my fears and grief. I knew that I had to come out of all those things [distress].” His mother was very supportive when he was undergoing psychotherapy. Formal and informal mental health care led to his quick recovery (P14 “S”, 21 years, bereaved brother and survivor of a deadly terror attack at school). Another study conducted by Christine Vaughn in 1976 revealed that the mental health outpatients who were only receiving acute hospital treatment showed good recovery, highlighting the role of family as a major variable in ensuring recovery from severe mental disorders. The study emphasized that negative attitudes and criticism resulted in patients’ relapse, while emotional warmth and supportive comments by the family resulted in better clinical outcomes for the patients (Falloon, 2003). This reveals that family and community care have a positive role in the recovery and treatment of adverse mental conditions and in enhancing the prognosis of patients.

Sibling Distraction and Emotional Regulation

A survivor from the bomb blast in Qissa Khwani Market [Peshwar] expresses the effect of the explosion on his mental health as “The sound of that explosion echoed in my mind for two months.” The quote represents the intense psychological effects of the blast on the survivor. It shows that apart from the physical damage, the emotional scars persist well beyond the event, showing that the survivor needs mental healthcare. Usually, such survivors require trauma-informed care; however, in this case, the survivor’s family took the lead to support him in recovering. He describes his support system as, all my brothers are older than me, and they love me a lot. They came and took me home to my village. They would take care of me by getting me treated, taking me to the hospital now and then, and bringing me medicine.” The survivor emphasized that his healing process could be attributed to his family, indicating that support from family members is essential for a person to recover from trauma. In his case, the support given by his family filled the void in the healthcare system. Post-incident, the survivor also got married in 2019, which resulted in a positive change in him. Marriage brought a notable change in his life and shifted his life’s direction. His focus diverted towards family life [wife and children], which suggests that personal relationships help strengthen a person’s recovery and offer them a sense of direction. Even in formal mental health therapeutic services, such supportive relationships play an integral part. The survivor’s interpersonal relationships, including brothers, wife, and children, acted as a primary source of strength and stability. The survivor emphasized that his parents offered him unconditional care, which gave him motivation and comfort and supported his recovery. He stated that “My parent comfort meant everything to me,” and “family support was the most important one” indicating a clear preference of the survivor for family over institutional support. He did not take any formal or homeopathic treatments for his mental health (“S” 26 years, survivor of bomb blast in Qissa Khwani Market, Peshawar). Henry Richardson was a physician who, in 1948, described the role of family care in the recovery of physical and mental health problems. His famous book “Patients Have Families” became the foundation of a systemic approach to family interventions and was adopted by a group of social anthropologists and psychiatrists at a research institute in California. Earlier, psychoanalytically trained professionals suggested that family influence has a major role in the development of serious mental illnesses. After Richardson’s book, it was largely believed that family care could also influence the recovery processes. This suggests that the family system was the root cause of mental ailments for many years until the pioneers of family treatment researched the role of communication styles within families while dealing with daily life issues. Residential research (for up to two years) conducted at the National Institute of Health (NIH) in Bethesda provided evidence for it. It was observed that regular family meetings provided the families with an opportunity to openly discuss their problems and solutions to the persistent issues, which had a considerable therapeutic impact. During the same era, British social psychiatrists and sociologists conducted studies that proved that relocating the mental health patients into their community settings was helpful in their recovery due to the provision of a household interpersonal environment. A worse outcome was observed in studies where individuals resided in hostels where support and warmth were lacking (Falloon, 2003).

A traumatized survivor reported that after the incident, he was surrounded by his siblings and relatives [cousins] most of the time for two months. They would come to ask about his well-being. He recounted, “My sister, who is younger than me, would come for not a day or two only, but repeatedly she would come to stay with me, to console me, and show that I am not alone, and someone is with me. This is the kind of support that I received.” But during the third month, when their arrival was reduced, he would feel their absence and fear in solitude. He expressed this by saying: “I used to visit uninvited weddings to meet people, and to surround myself with people, just to avoid the solitude”. This represents that post-incident, the initial phase of healing was supported by his family members, in the presence of whom he felt safe and secure. He said that there were some formal mental

health care facilities around, which he had not visited much to date. He iterated, “In the initial phase [post-trauma] I went two to three times [for formal treatment], but afterwards, I did not visit, because I felt I was getting better in the presence of my family. Family support has greatly helped in my recovery.” (“A”, 42 years, police survivor of terrorist attack). There was also evidence that family members were overburdened and stressed by the care of their relatives, but in Pakistani culture and tradition, the family kinship system prevails, where family members take pride in looking after their family. Since the current study focuses on the survivors of political violence who mainly go through PTSD, grief, and depressive features that mainly resemble the aspects of neurosis, and not psychosis, family intervention can play a positive therapeutic role with such neurotic survivors by providing empathy and consistent support (Falloon, 2003).

Psychological first aid carries significance in the recovery process. A survivor of a huge bomb blast reported that she went through a tough time by watching the undesirable dead bodies and injuries, mainly of children, after the incident. She felt helpless when she could not save many children who were martyred in the incident. She explains that after reaching home, her elder brother offered her first aid support, “The very first thing my brother did was ... giving me two relaxant tablets so that I could get some sleep.” She said that her brother supported her throughout and showed a caring presence, which helped her emotionally. Four months later, she left the country [for Malaysia] to completely avoid the trauma site and memories. She said that her brother understood her situation the most and kept supporting her. He used to say that “No one can see these hidden wounds except for those who experience them”. His understanding provided her with mental comfort and consolation and evoked feelings of relief and validation. “This made me feel that I am not alone in this pain, and someone is sharing my experience”, so the survivor did not feel isolated in her trauma. She further reported that, “My sister was concerned about my well-being and monitored my mood and behavior now and then. She would advise me to look after myself and not to pay heed to things that disturb me. I think that family has a very important role in the recovery of a survivor ... if there is no family support, you cannot even reach the hospital. Only family support can take a traumatized person out of hell.” This suggests that the survivor was protected by her siblings, which made her feel safe and heard; this assisted in taking her out of her trauma. It also helped her recover from her distress and grief, which she labelled as ‘hell’ (P10 “S”, 36 years, survivor of terrorist attack). In a study, Kliapets (2015) suggests that family plays a therapeutic role in overcoming traumatic experiences. The war in Ukraine resulted in death and destruction, and many survivors directly or indirectly experienced the trauma as people were forced to leave their homes, friends, jobs, and experienced unwanted change in their lives. Fear of life, worry, lack of safety, and uncertainty of the future existed in the citizens of Ukraine. The country lacked high-quality psychological services and relied on family support as psychotherapeutic intervention. Family serves the function of ‘spontaneous therapeutic sessions’ by offering interfamily verbal and non-verbal communication, which aims to create mutual understanding between them. Without any timetables and formats, the family aims to offer caressing and resonating through these (informal) sessions. In this way, family members help each other in the assessment of their ideas, viewpoints, self-realization, and enhancement in personality development. Family offers to construct trustful relations, relaxing and restoring oneself, and resting one’s psychological mechanisms (Kliapets, 2015).

Spousal Support and Rebuilding Identity

A survivor of target killing reported that his spouse’s emotional support and prayers helped him regain a positive self-image after the [target killing] attacks on him in South Waziristan. He recounted, “My wife used to pray for me, she was worried about my safety, her prayers helped me recover”. In formal mental healthcare, the therapist tries to reconstruct the identity of the patient, while in this case, the wife’s continued emotional support and special prayers appeared to build the survivor identity and self-esteem, which got shaky after going through the attacks (“T” 40 years, survivor of multiple targets killing attacks in S. Waziristan).

Likewise, a traumatized wife of a bomb blast survivor explained that she was comparatively more disturbed due to the incident than her husband. The incident put a sudden psychological toll on her and her family due to her husband’s critical injuries and his loss of function to look after family matters and finances. During this adverse phase, her elder brother appeared to her as an angel. She said, “My elder brother helped me morally and financially, which is what I needed the most at the time. He also arranged a big room for me at the hospital [to stay along with my husband] and provided so many facilities that I stayed there for a week.” This suggests that she received complete emotional, logistical, and financial support from her elder brother, which helped her relieve her stress. She reported that, “My brother supported me greatly, without whom it would have been impossible for me to handle everything.” She also overcame her emotional struggle with the presence and care offered by her young

children. They were a source of motivation and emotional strength for her. She explained their [emotional] support as, “My eldest son, who supports me more than my husband, often says, Mama! let’s go for a walk and try not to think about the problems [caused by the incident]” and when her son returned from the hospital, he strengthened her by saying “Mama! Don’t worry! Papa is alive, and everything will be alright!” This suggests that children, though young, also offer emotional support and become a source of empowerment for their parents, with the help of which they surpass the challenging situations. She fulfilled her responsibilities towards her children during this stressful time as a mother and father, both, which supported her husband’s mental health and recovery, as she took on his responsibilities too. She expressed, “I never forgot to give my children the time and education they deserved. One of my sons was in nursery class at the time, and he secured first position.” This suggests that the mother ensured a sense of order and routine for her children in times of crisis, which supported their psychological well-being and growth as well. She also received encouragement from her husband when he expressed and recognized her care and support post-incident. This reflects the importance of family support in the recovery process. She described her husband’s [survivors] encouragement of care as, “He used to tell me that while looking after him, I never expressed any remarks of favor on him, representing how much I cared”, which built a sense of belongingness and unconditional love between the spouses. He expressed his feelings by saying that “You took such good care of me that even my wound didn’t develop any infections or cause any pain.” This suggests that his wife offered him a complete nursing facility at home in his comfort zone. She said, “After this incident, he finally understood what his family was like [the value of his family].” She expressed the significance of her family’s [brother’s and parents] unconditional care for her husband and how he began to appreciate the role of his wife and children in his recovery, emphasizing the blended nature of emotional and physical care. He expressed it as, “You [wife] and your elder brother gave me a new life... He appreciated me a lot after this incident.” (“A”, 44 years, traumatized wife of a survivor of bomb blast).

These statements illustrate the husband’s positive shift concerning the concept of family, which is particularly important during stressful situations. This also suggests that such crises strengthen the bond of a family. This case represents that in the absence of formal mental healthcare, the survivor’s wife and her elder brother managed his acute psychological pain resulting from the trauma. Kliapets (2015) suggests that family also offers a recreational function, wherein it offers joyful communication between the family members, joining common activities, supervising the activity of each other, planning entertainment together, which promotes the idea of ‘we’ and serves a psychotherapeutic function. Hence, family promotes the psychological health of other family members and assists in their personal development. Family serves to be a ‘fortress’ which offers protection and acceptance regardless of its members’ appearance, status, financial state, life principles, and other differences. Apart from this, family also provides other assistance, including education, reproduction, recreation, regulation, sexual, and economic assistance. Family provides psychological safety, personality development, and liking to its members. Family creates a friendly emotional environment at home, which helps in the psychological recovery of family members in times of crisis. The psychological safety that a family member experiences promotes confidence to deal with life stressors.

Communities are usually targeted in contemporary conflicts. Like in Waziristan, the whole community suffered. The military tactics not only target the civilians but also disrupt specific community structures to shatter the sense of safety for the individuals living there, to challenge their status quo, or their willpower to fight. Such terror results in destroying the livelihood of individuals, separating them from community resources, disrupting the individuals’ supportive relationships, preventing social organizing, and disturbing their daily lives. Such contemporary wars result in immobilizing the people by instilling terror, anxiety, and despair (Farwell & Cole, 2001). Due to the militancy and insurgency in the South Waziristan region, since 2007, there has been an increase in the incidents of target killings involving tribal leaders, military personnel, or specific individuals perceived to be assisting the government. A survivor of such target killing by unknown men reported that he had earlier lost his elder brother in a target killing attack, while he [himself] survived. He had survived three such attacks, the last of which, however, caused damage to his group while crossing Mir Ali [a region] when gunfire was opened on them. He was not shot, but lost one of the tribal leaders to death, who was a close friend, in this attack. He faced symptoms of grief and PTSD afterwards. At those tough times, he reported, how his wife offered him support and assistance, “Masha Allah [As God has willed], my partner took great care of me as I was grieving... and my kids became a source of support for me too, without which my healing would not have been possible. I recovered due to their support and presence.” This quote highlights the significant role partners and children, as family members, play in providing emotional and practical support. The respondent acknowledges

their care, indicating that family plays a crucial role in mental well-being. Apart from that, he said that “My wife tried to keep me happy [during the crises] and avoided doing things that would bother me”. This suggests that his wife offered him an understanding and empathy that is a prerequisite in a formal therapeutic relationship, too. His wife’s efforts to identify and alleviate his sadness reflect a supportive environment that can be as effective as formal mental health interventions. Sharing personal experiences is welcomed by the family at any time. A family member is given the liberty not to inhibit their feelings or emotions, and they are assured that they will be accepted and loved unconditionally as they are. Family is a safe space for all, where no one intends to psychologically or physically injure another member (Kliapets, 2015).

The survivor also mentioned that his friends offered him support and assistance during times of crisis, which helped in mental peace and healing from trauma. He iterates, “I have a lot of good friends ... they were readily available for me when I needed them in any way... I didn’t have to ask them for their support; they offered me emotional and moral support and took me out of grief. Because of them, I felt energized and didn’t feel lonely.” This proposes that social support provides companionship and emotional relief, which benefits people in their recovery. Formal systems are insufficient and considered taboo in regions like Waziristan, driving people to seek refuge in family and social networks. On the other hand, culturally, the family and social network look after the mental health needs of survivors (“M”, 55 years, survivor of target killing in Waziristan). In Ukraine, overcoming the outcome of traumatic events is purely a family task. They prefer conversation with family members (including husband or wife, father or mother, or a friend) as a psychotherapy, because the culture of psychological assistance is not well-developed. However, in Europe and America, high-quality psychological assistance is available, and the population has the orientation that specialist support is available in case of need. Hence, in Ukraine, family is a space that carries ‘therapeutic potential’, which helps in overcoming the symptoms of traumatic incidents (Kliapets, 2015).

A survivor of a bomb blast reported that his mother and wife’s unconditional love and support helped him heal through his trauma. His wife and mother were the first ones to identify [diagnose] that he is suffering from mental trauma. As a result, he said that “they looked after me a lot, held my hands, and gave me support ... they provided me a lot of support, which gave me relief”. This suggests that the survivor spouse and mother understood him and his feelings better than anyone and, as a result, helped him heal from his trauma (“A”, 42 years, police survivor of terrorist attack). The psychological support that family members and relatives offer increases the possibility of solving life problems. The family offers resources that people could use when they require them. Psychological support within families offers fulfilment of the needs of acceptance, joy, and respect. The family provides psychological and intellectual support to its members. The psychological support includes sympathizing, empathizing with problems, and assisting in problem solving, while the intellectual support includes analyzing and resolving the outcomes of traumatic incidents (Kliapets, 2015). Another survivor of the deadly police line bomb blast also highlighted that his wife and daughters offered him consistent physical and emotional support, and his elder brother’s advice at the time of crisis was commendable and strengthened him (“T”, 41 years, survivor of police line mosque attack). The [second] wife of a bereaved father [who had previously faced the death of his first wife due to Hepatitis] supported her husband’s traumatic journey by totally changing her attitude toward him. She was having some adjustment problems with him, but when she saw that he was experiencing the death grief of his only son [from the former wife], she changed her attitude positively towards him to provide him comfort and consolation. He reported that “Looking at a change in my behavior [due to grief], she completely changed her attitude into positivity. And since the martyrdom of my son, there have been no issues between me and my wife as such. The trauma strengthened our bond.” (“F”, 49 years, bereaved father of a martyred son in the school massacre) Attempting to understand, sympathize, and share the pain decreases the burden on family members going through difficult times. The intellectual support also offers drafting strategies to overcome the consequences of traumatic incidents, offering a safe space for its realization, and utilizing external resources that could offer psychological help, like relatives, friends, or specialists, etc. (Kliapets, 2015).

References

- De Zulueta, F. (2007). *From pain to violence: The traumatic roots of destructiveness*. Wiley.
- Falloon, I. R. (2003). Family interventions for mental disorders: efficacy and effectiveness. *World Psychiatry*, 2(1), 20.
- Farwell, N., & Cole, J. B. (2001). Community as a context of healing. *International Journal of Mental Health*, 30(4), 19-41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207411.2001.11449530>
- Gadit, A. A. (2003). Health services delivery by shamans: A local experience in Pakistan. *International Journal of Mental Health*, 32(2), 63–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207411.2003.11449585>
- Government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. (2017). *District Health Information System (DHIS) annual report 2017*. Health Department, Government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. <https://healthkp.gov.pk>
- Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA). (2018). *Data collection survey on health facilities & equipment in the Islamic Republic of Pakistan: Final report*. JICA. <https://openjicareport.jica.go.jp>
- Khan, A., Ullah, O., Nawaz, K., & Ahmad, I. (2018). Post traumatic stress disorder among school children of Army Public School Peshawar after Six month of terrorists attack. *Pakistan journal of medical sciences*, 34(3), 525. <https://doi.org/10.12669/pjms.343.14885>
- Kliapets, O. (2015). Family as a space for recovering from traumas. *Education Sciences and Psychology*, (5), 70-73.
- Kurji, Z., Premani, Z. S., & Mithani, Y. (2016). Analysis of the health care system of Pakistan: Lessons learnt and way forward. *Journal of Ayub Medical College Abbottabad*, 28(3), 601–604. <http://jamc.ayubmed.edu.pk>
- Sashidharan, S. P., White, R., Mezzina, R., Jansen, S., & Gishoma, D. (2016). Global mental health in high-income countries. *The British Journal of Psychiatry: The Journal of Mental Science*, 209(1), 3–5. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.bp.115.179556>
- Sehat Kahani. (2022). Make mental health a priority in Pakistan. *Sehat Kahani*. <https://sehatkahani.com/make-mental-health-a-priority-in-pakistan/>
- Sikander, S. (2020). Mental health services in Pakistan: Challenges and solutions. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 7(11), 933–935. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(20\)30301-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(20)30301-1)
- Sohail, M. M., Latif, A., & Lodhi, F. S. (2017). Mental health in Pakistan: A call for integration in primary health care. *Journal of Ayub Medical College Abbottabad*, 29(2), 252–255. <http://jamc.ayubmed.edu.pk/index.php/jamc/article/view/1499>
- Sohail, S. A., Syed, A. A., & Rahman, A. (2017). Mental health in Pakistan: Yesterday, today and tomorrow. In *International and Cultural Psychology* (pp. 17–37). Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-7999-5_2
- South Asia Terrorism Portal. (2023). Terrorist and other militant groups in Pakistan. *Congress.gov*. <https://www.congress.gov/crs-product/IF11934>
- World Health Organization. (2009). *WHO-AIMS report on mental health system in Pakistan*. WHO & Ministry of Health, Pakistan. https://www.who.int/mental_health/pakistan_who_aims_report.pdf